

What do we want from Research Software?

Wishlists for the future of RSE

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* This is a write-up of the discussion session that took place at the RSLondonSouthEast 2020 workshop in February 2020. The session involved all workshop participants and we would therefore like to credit all attendees with contributing to this material. See the end of the article for further details.

Introduction

In February 2020, nearly 100 people with an interest in research software gathered at The Royal Society in London for the 2nd annual [RSLondonSouthEast workshop](#) – the flagship annual event of [RSLondon](#), the London and South East regional research software community. The workshop was supported by [UKRI-EPSRC](#) and the [Society of Research Software Engineering](#). Attendees included people from a wide range of roles including Research Software Engineers (RSEs), researchers, academics and systems professionals, all with an interest in working with, building or supporting research software, or finding out more about what's going on in the community.

In addition to two keynote speakers and multiple talks around research software, the workshop included a discussion session and this article is a write up of the outcomes from that session. The aim of the discussion was to identify “wishlists” of things that the participants would most like to see happening or developing around one of four different topics. The participants were divided into 8 groups of roughly equal size (8-10 people), and two groups were assigned to each of the 4 topics. Participants were free to choose their preferred group/topic.

The Topics

The four topic areas for the discussion were chosen as key areas that we believe cover the full breadth of the RSE domain. They also reflect the “four pillars” highlighted in the recently published article [“The Four Pillars of Research Software Engineering”](#). The areas discussed were:

- Policy
- Training
- Community
- Software Development

Groups were asked to come up with the 5 most important things that they would like to see in the area that they were considering. At the end of the session, each group reported back on their 5 top items. Here we summarise the session outputs, highlighting the 5 most important points for each and then providing some further discussion, added by the editors, for each point.

Topic 1: POLICY

Policy has been of huge importance to research software over recent years. With individuals and groups lobbying at the institutional and national levels, we have seen RSE becoming increasingly important and better represented in policy decisions. This has led to the emergence of RSE

groups at many institutions, funding for RSEs on projects and the setup of [EPSRC's RSE Fellowship scheme](#). What did the workshop participants think were the most important things they'd like to see in the area of policy?

1) *Ability to include money specifically for software maintenance in grant applications*

Funding is always a challenge and a major requirement within the research community, so it's no surprise that a funding-related point has come at the top of the list for the "policy" area. Funding is very often focused towards the initial building of innovative software or extending software with very specific functionality. The way that research funding is allocated to specifically timed projects with key aims doesn't lend itself well to the more general maintenance tasks that are required to ensure on-going software reliability. The process of fixing bugs, tweaking functionality and making minor extensions to tools and applications to address user requirements can be a very time consuming and unpredictable process. Different approaches to applying for and accessing support for general research software maintenance could clearly be valuable and would offer the potential to sustain applications and tools that may otherwise stagnate or get abandoned. This would also help research software professionals to gain enhanced recognition for their work.

2) *Inclusion of software sustainability requirements and potential support for software that underpins key research communities in proposals*

This second funding/proposal-related point goes beyond software maintenance to highlight the importance of sustainability tasks that are required to ensure on-going availability and sustainability of software. Making applications production-ready and scaling them to support larger numbers of users are also important aspects here. It is also not uncommon for open source research software to become widely adopted within a community and to end up underpinning significant elements of work being done in that community. At the same time, such software is often still maintained by the original developer(s) who are often overloaded with their current software work and/or research. There are not currently clear and direct approaches for addressing support for such software. Maintaining availability of software so that it can be built on by others requires that there are supported, open repositories and software archiving services available to all.

3) *Job stability and growing support for and understanding the need for "directly allocated" RSEs*

If you're familiar with the way that funding works in the UK academic community, you'll know that permanent members of academic/research staff are often funded as "directly allocated" resources while researchers, and often RSEs, who are funded on specific projects for a fixed time period are generally supported via "directly incurred" costs. "[Directly allocated](#)" costs are the costs of a resource used in a project, where the same resource can also be used in other activities. On the other hand, "[directly incurred](#)" costs are those explicitly arising from the project, though the resource may not always be exclusive to the project e.g. if an RSE's time is shared between projects the relevant proportion would be charged to each project. For RSEs, who may have the expertise to undertake smaller pieces of work across a wide range of different projects providing significant research value to a number of research teams, the directly allocated costing model is much more appropriate. However there are rarely opportunities for this model to be used since it is likely to require institutional financial support and underpinning by institutions. This is a major area of importance in RSE policy making.

4) *Recognising RSE outputs in national research assessment activities*

A huge amount of weight within the academic community is placed on the outputs of large-scale research assessment activities such as REF. These exercises have a major bearing on how funding is allocated and can make a significant difference to the fortunes of departments and institutions over a multi-year period. RSEs tend to be lost within such activities and this, in turn, can remove much of the incentive to look at providing departmental or institutional-level funding for more research-focused RSEs. Traditional metrics of success such as paper outputs and the locations where they are published don't tend to apply to RSEs, or RSEs are at least often unable to compete with academics in such areas. As the importance of RSEs is being recognised within communities, this recognition, and the investigation of approaches to support and address it, needs to transfer to institutional and national research management levels. At the workshop, there was a brief mention of plans around an initiative to make visible other types of research outcomes in addition to articles, which was launched a few days after (see <https://hidden-ref.org/>) .

5) *Guidance on the use of funds to support open source*

While open source software might be free at the point of use, there are still the extensive costs of building and maintaining it that are ultimately taken on by research funding or commercial entities. This somewhat indirect route of funding software that can sometimes be used by many thousands or even millions of people and the suggestion in relation to this point is that there may be better and more direct ways to support such software. This could, for example, include paying “maintenance contracts” to an entity like [NumFocus](#), which is a fiscal sponsor for open source projects, to help take on and support key applications or tools used extensively within specific research domains; or establishment of programmes (such as [CZI](#) Essential Software for Science) that explicitly fund maintenance development. More guidance on this new funding model is needed.

Topic 2: TRAINING

Research Software Engineers tend to have advanced and wide-ranging skill sets. Such ranges of skills take time to develop and keep up to date, so training is important to RSEs. That doesn't necessarily mean attending training courses – many RSEs choose to teach themselves new skills, either by working through online training materials or just by using new tools, reading blog posts and documentation to assist them when they encounter problems and sharing community best practices. As an RSE, learning a new technology, programming language or tool can often be time-critical. The other side of training is that RSEs are often involved in providing training to students, researchers, academics or other RSEs. The points represented in the feedback from the groups discussing training cover both these areas:

1) *Opportunities to help RSEs grow their skills in the non-programming aspects of being an RSE*

Three particular areas were highlighted as important topics for training: *project management, resource and time estimation* and *project delivery*. These are all aspects of working on software projects that RSEs are likely to need to learn more about as they progress in an RSE career. In particular, these are topics that are of key importance to RSE group leaders. Since the RSE group leader role is relatively new and the number of groups is growing, providing such training opportunities has the potential to offer real impact in the near-term.

2) *Developing software at scale*

As data volumes and compute requirements increase, RSEs are more likely to be asked to work with complex data- and compute-intensive scientific codes. There are specialist topics that individuals can look to obtain training in such as GPU development, working with FPGAs, Machine Learning algorithms, etc. However, there are also more general best practices that can be applied to large-scale software development and also to managing infrastructure to support large-scale applications. Better support for training in these topics, techniques and areas would be beneficial to individual RSEs but also to the wider community.

3) Pedagogy / Becoming better at delivering training material

As highlighted above, RSEs often find themselves involved in delivering training. This may involve anything from teaching [Carpentries](#) material or delivering self-developed training materials to reasonable-sized groups of participants in a fairly standard classroom environment to offering small group technical skills training as part of “clinic” sessions run by an RSE team or community. For most people, it would be beneficial to have some element of training into how to effectively teach new material to others. While the Carpentries instructor training courses cover this extensively, this is an area that is often missed in other environments. This tends to be because there is limited time/resources available or because there are not enough people, or no people, with the skills to teach the material. This is something that it would be beneficial for the Research Software Engineering community to have access to.

4) Developing better outreach processes for skills/knowledge exchange

In this context, we consider that training also encompasses a variety of skills/knowledge exchange that is often achieved through community seminars, networking and discussion events. The value of these informal exchanges that provide a direct means to learn new technical skills, or provide suggestions or recommendations on how/where to learn such skills, should not be underestimated. If processes can be improved so that these opportunities do not occur in an entirely ad hoc manner, there is scope to build on the availability of a community or links with collaborators to provide a basis for skills development.

5) Developing training links with non-academic institutions

The fifth item that was considered to be an important aspect in the context of training is the development of links with non-academic institutions. Industry training can sometimes be delivered differently to academic training as a result of different aims and drivers. It is believed that there is much to be learnt from different approaches to delivering technical materials and there is also a wealth of knowledge and expertise in the industry environment that could be shared with research software teams and vice versa. By developing training links with non-academic institutions, it is considered that there will be a benefit to both the academic and industrial partners.

Topic 3: COMMUNITY

The RSE community has grown significantly [since the role was coined in 2014](#), and this is shown by the popularity of events such as the RSLondonSouthEast workshop and the RSE conference. In terms of aspects that will help the RSE community to develop further, participants at the RSLondonSouthEast workshop felt that a better convergence between RSEs, academics and industry might be needed. Further interaction with academics is important to highlight the RSE role, and how we can contribute to the acceleration of scientific discoveries by providing the much

needed software engineering skills in the development of research software. We now highlight and expand on 5 key points highlighted in the feedback from the groups discussing “community”:

1) *Better convergence between RSEs, academics and industry communities*

The nature of the RSE role means that it tends to fall somewhere in between the role of a researcher and that of a professional software developer in industry. On the one side, RSEs are much more aligned to the researcher role in terms of the environment they work in and their day-to-day work. On the other hand, there is a lot that RSEs can learn from industry practices and the approaches and skills used by developers in industry. Similarly, there is also a lot that industry developers can learn from the way that projects operate in a research environment and the challenges with undertaking research work. As such, there are many opportunities to share experiences between RSE communities and industry-based software communities and better convergence between the two groups would be valuable.

2) *Improve opportunities for knowledge and code sharing and publishing event outputs*

One of the core benefits of a community is the ability to share knowledge and experiences with peers and develop new skills. To enable this, there need to be suitable events and platforms for sharing this information and for publishing the outputs of events such as workshops and conferences. This is something that could be improved in the RSE community. Not necessarily because there is a lack of blog posts, community activities and publishing of event outputs, but often because these outputs are made available across a huge range of different platforms and cannot always be easily found. As a result, we need to find new ways to share our outputs and improve the opportunities available to community members to access them and participate by making use of available material and sharing their own materials.

3) *Building different types of communities or setting up sub-communities, e.g. around commercialisation for research software*

At present, communities in the RSE space tend to be quite general. As the number of RSEs or individuals working in the area continues to grow significantly, there will be greater calls for new communities or branches of existing communities that address specific aspects of the RSE domain. As we reach a critical mass of individuals who can sustain these more focused communities, we need to be proactive in setting them up, or supporting the individuals who want to take this on themselves. Commercialisation of research software is an area highlighted in the discussion where there is already interest in a specialist community.

4) *RSE community ambassadors to help support, promote and grow RSE communities*

Building, growing and sustaining RSE communities is challenging and time consuming. Beyond the general aspects of running a community, such as planning and running events, writing up newsletters, etc., there is the challenge of raising the community's profile and promoting it to potential new members. One of the suggestions arising from the community discussion groups was to create “RSE Ambassadors”. These would be individuals who are enthusiastic about promoting and growing a local or regional community. Ambassadors across communities may be linked together by a network where they can share ideas and experiences and there may also be scope to train community ambassadors and in large, successful communities, give them official, funded roles.

5) *Strengthen outreach within institutions and to the wider research community, e.g. via blogs, webinars, etc.*

Building on some of the previous points, this fifth point is more general and highlights the importance of strengthening outreach activities, both within RSE communities and beyond, targeting the wider research community. This may be done through events, blog posts, webinars and other outreach mechanisms but the importance of this point is in highlighting the existence of Research Software Engineering and the work that RSEs do to support others within the research community. If RSE is to continue to grow and gain recognition, the importance of strengthening outreach activities cannot be underestimated.

Topic 4: SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

The final discussion topic – Software Development – resulted in the largest number of ideas and suggestions. This is unsurprising since software development is the core element of Research Software Engineering. As we've seen with the discussion and suggestions in the above topics, the RSE domain includes a wide range of other aspects that are all important in ensuring its sustainability and growth. However, for individuals undertaking RSE-type work, it is likely that software development takes up most of their time and is what probably motivated them to do their current job. The discussions around software development are summarised below.

1) Provide ways to make it easier to understand what software you need for a given task

There is so much software out there, it's often difficult to know what the right library is for a particular task. The general approach, without advice or suggestions from colleagues or collaborators, is to look at the different options and see which of them claim to do what you want. Then you might look at user feedback, how active a project is, how well is it maintained, etc. Nonetheless, it's often the case that a library is chosen and then a little way down the line, it turns out to be the wrong choice! This can be inefficient and a community-supported means of highlighting potential good choices of libraries and applications for common RSE tasks could be a valuable resource. This may include a database of experts who can help provide advice on the right software to use for a particular problem, or an online directory of software targeted specifically at RSEs¹.

2) Full-stack Open Source: Make use of open source libraries at the top and bottom of the stack

Open source libraries and tools are available for just about anything that the research developer may want to build. It was highlighted that using open source software and tooling at every level of the software stack, from databases, application servers and frameworks, through to numerical processing libraries and front-end web frameworks and visualisation tools is a viable option.

3) Support interoperability and software designed to simplify software pipelines

This point brings together a few different comments and areas discussed by the two groups covering this topic. On the software pipelines side, there was discussion around workflow management and the importance of raising awareness of tools that can make life easier for research developers. Using common and widely supported tools can help with distributing pipelines and associated processes to researchers who are the end-users of the code. On the more general point of interoperability, the general importance of ensuring that code is interoperable across different target environments and platforms was highlighted.

¹ Note that subsequent to the RSLondonSouthEast 2020 workshop, the [Research Software Encyclopedia](#) has been launched which provides an example of a tool that fulfils this role.

4) *Building support for research-related software development into Integrated Development Environments (IDEs)*

Modern IDEs are tremendously powerful and extensible. Adding support to IDEs for research-related tasks could help to simplify an RSEs work. This might be anything from including support for parsing and verifying citation files within a project, to adding domain-specific annotations to code that are targeted at researchers. There was also mention of support for mathematical notation in comments and support for developing mathematical code, and simplifying/optimising two-factor authentication. There is a lot of scope here and an advisory group could potentially be set up to identify a first set of important features and functionality that could be added to IDEs with a view to developing a specification and reference implementation.

5) *Tools for data checking and data governance*

With research data volumes growing continually and a vast expansion in the number of data sources, it is complex to work with data and to ensure that it is valid and used correctly, in accordance with any assigned permissions. The software development discussion groups raised various data-related points. On data cleaning/formatting, there was a suggestion that a tool similar to “linting” tools used for code correctness/formatting checks could be used – “data lint”. This could form a key aspect of helping to check that data meets various criteria and could be run automatically in the same way that code linters are. On the data governance side, there were suggestions around tools and approaches for helping to ensure data privacy and helping RSEs to understand and address governance issues.

Recommendations and takeaways

In writing up the discussion around the session outputs, the editors have come up with some recommendations that we’d like to propose as items for comment by the wider community. We highlight what we see as the two most important *concrete* recommendations for each topic.

Policy:

- **Create new code maintenance funds to sustain codes developed in research projects beyond project completion:** Funds would be available from the end of a project for some extended period (e.g. up to twice the original project length). Funding would be limited to a maximum percentage of the total project cost and could be used at any time during the validity period but project teams would need to be able to demonstrate that the funds were being used to directly support code maintenance on project outputs. This could be applied for as part of a grant proposal or it could be done at the institution level via a Software Maintenance fund similar to the Impact Accelerator funds.
- **Lobby institutions and funders to develop stronger guidelines for permanent roles that support RSEs both within central teams and also within academic departments:** Senior RSEs and those with a more research-focused role are likely to be capable of applying for and obtaining funding, either as a PI or as a Co-I. In order to support this, institutions need to offer more scope and opportunity to set up permanent RSE roles that can be underwritten and supported through a directly allocated funding model.

Training:

- **Develop a short RSE trainers course that can be used to give RSEs a general background in good teaching practices:** This would provide very basic level material but would at least ensure that RSEs could receive some general examples, ideas and suggestions of teaching best practice.
- **Run an industry/RSE training workshop that brings together a group of RSEs from the research community and a group of representatives (including RSEs where possible) from industry to look at potential crossovers and shared training opportunities.**

Community:

- **Develop and publish a set of RSE community best practices for building and sustaining communities.**
- **Set up an RSE Ambassadors programme at a national level with ambassadors being recruited from local and regional RSE communities.**

Software Development:

- **Develop an RSE software directory listing recommended applications, tools and libraries for a range of common research software tasks:** The directory would offer advice and examples and would provide a place for users of the tools to highlight good, or not so good experiences with the software in the directory. Anyone would be able to submit applications to the directory but this would be done with a submission form that would undergo lightweight review to identify that submissions are genuine.
- **Develop a prototype RSE plugin for a common IDE (e.g. Visual Studio Code) to demonstrate some of the potential benefits of such a tool and to start building a group of interested individuals to take this forward.**

Contributors

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